

A new scale for rice sheath blight (ShB) disease assessment

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Using varietal resistance to minimize ShB damage is the least explored ShB management component. The level of resistance in most commercial cultivars is not high enough to protect rice plants from severe damage in highly conducive environments. However, combined with other disease control measures, such as chemical application or cultural practices, it could play a significant role in an integrated program. Improved resistance in modern rice cultivars is important in sustaining rice productivity in ShB-prone areas.

An efficient and reliable ShB screening method requires a quantitative scale that differentiates varietal reactions. Conventional grading of disease levels is arbitrary, without considering estimated yield losses. To improve this system, a scale was developed based on the relationship between ShB severity and yield loss (see table).

Rating on relative lesion height (RLH) is easier and faster to use in a uniformly inoculated mass-screening nursery, but rating on sheath position also can be used. The relative position and length of sheaths at different positions in different cultivars are uniform, except in extremely tall cultivars (see figure). Actual measurement of plant and lesion height is recommended, since visual estimation of RLH is often biased. Staggered planting of groups of entries with similar maturity and height would allow a better comparison.

Under favorable environments, highly susceptible cultivars would be rated more than grade 7, and descriptive classification can be directly applied. Otherwise, standardizing or adjusting the descriptive classification to the infection level of locally known susceptible cultivars is needed.

Scale for rice ShB evaluation. IRRI, 1986.

Grade	RLH ^a (%)	Sheath position ^b	Relative disease intensity	Yield reduction ^c (%)	Classification ^d
0	0	0	0	0	HR
1	< 20	<4	1	1	R
3	20-30	3-4	5	1-5	MR
5	31-45	2	20	6-15	MS
7	46-65	1	50	16-30	S
9	>65	>1	100	>30	HS

^aRelative lesion height (%) = $\frac{\text{lesion height}}{\text{plant height}} \times 100$. ^b1 = uppermost sheath with flag leaf. ^cEstimated yield reduction in milled rice under pressure. ^dHR = highly resistant, R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible.

Rating scheme of a new scale for ShB mass screening. IRRI, 1986. Relative sheath positions were based on 30 cultivars grown under upland conditions. Values in parentheses show standard error of mean.

For rapid disease assessment in field plots or screening nursery, ShB severity (average disease intensity of a plant population) can be computed:

$$\text{Severity (25 DAF)} = \frac{0(N_0) + 1(N_1) + 5(N_3) + 20(N_5) + 50(N_7) + 100(N_9)}{\text{Total number of tillers or hills observed}}$$

where DAF = days after flowering,
 $N_0 - N_9$ = no. of tillers/hill classified by grade.

Relative disease intensity was calculated using midvalues of the estimated ranges of yield losses in each grade. A detailed disease assessment should consider leaf or sheath area in each position. □